

THE PROPERTIES OF A SILICON-CONTAINING ARYLACETYLENE RESIN MODIFIED BY OCTA(AZIDOPROPYL) POLYHEDRAL OLIGOMERIC SILSESQUIOXANE AND ITS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Silicon-containing arylacetylene (PSA) resins possess excellent performances, including high thermal stability, low dielectric constant, and high mechanical property maintenance at high temperature. Polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes (POSS) exhibits special organic-inorganic properties, which is usually used for the modification of polymeric materials.

A novel resin OAPS-PSA was obtained from PSA resin and octa(azidopropyl) polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (OAPS) by “click” polymerization. The structures and properties of the OAPS-PSA resins are characterized by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and contact angle measurements. The results show that the ethynyls or ethynylenes in the PSA resin can react with azide groups in OAPS through “click” polymerization to form triazole rings. The contact angle measurements illustrate that the surface of OAPS-PSA thermoset has higher polarity than that of the PSA thermoset.

The T300/OAPS-PSA and T300/PSA composites were prepared from 2D T300 carbon fiber plain fabrics, OAPS-PSA resin or PSA resin, respectively. The structures and properties of the composites were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), mechanical property tests, etc. The flexural property results indicate the flexural strength of a T300 /OAPS-PSA composite arrives at 293 MPa and increases by 24% as compared with that of the T300/PSA composite. The enhanced property is considered to be the contribution of the POSS with triazole rings formed in curing process.

INTRODUCTION

In recently years, the researches on the polymer materials with polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (POSS) have grown dramatically¹. With an inorganic and silica-like core surrounded by organic groups, the nano-sized POSS is represented by the formula $\text{RSiO}_{1.5}$ ². They are accessible by hydrolysis of trifunctional RSiY_3 molecules and can be modified by a number of substitution reactions.

The wide range of functional R groups makes POSS molecules particularly useful. The introduction of the POSS into polymers could substantially enhance the mechanical properties, thermal behavior, flame retardant properties, and improve dielectric properties of the polymers^{3,4,5,6,7}. Many novel POSS-containing polymers with well-defined topological structure have been prepared by using copper free or copper-catalyzed azide/alkyne 1, 3-dipolar cycloaddition named “click” reaction^{8,9,10}.

The silicon-containing arylacetylene (PSA) resin composed of $[-(R_1)Si(R_2)-C\equiv C-Ar-C\equiv C-]$ possesses better thermal stability¹¹, that is, high decomposition temperature and high residue yields, compared with polyarylacetylene (PAA), which is known for its outstanding heat resistance. Besides, it performs excellent mechanical properties, dielectric properties and high temperature ceramic-produced performance¹²⁻¹³.

The versatile investigations on the PSA resin have been undertaken. Liu et al. used nickel acetylacetonate to reduce the curing temperature of PSA resin¹⁴. An effective way to improve its properties is by changing the structure of the PSA. Gao et al. have designed and prepared a series of PSA resins with various dimethylsiloxane unit lengths¹⁵. Wang et al. incorporated *o*-carborane with PSA, and this carborane-containing polymer processed excellent thermooxidative stability¹⁶. Gao et al. synthesized aniline-based bifunctional BZs and prepared PSA/BZs blends to enhance the mechanical properties¹⁷. Li et al. synthesized and characterized a arylacetylene oligomer containing POSS units in main chains¹⁸. However, the POSS unit is not easily obtained. Jiang et al. synthesized 3-azidopropylheptaphenyl POSS and grafted the POSS on PSA through Huisgen azide-alkyne 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition¹³. The grafted PSA did not show good thermal stability.

In this work, a series of OAPS-PSA resins with various weight percentages were prepared from a PSA resin and octa(azidopropyl) POSS (OAPS) with thermal polymerization. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) was used to explore the extent of the reaction. The Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), static contact angle measurements were used to investigate the properties of the thermosets. The effects of OAPS on the mechanical properties of T300/OAPS-PSA composites were studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

All reagents were purchased and used without further purification unless stated otherwise. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was heated to reflux with sodium. PSA was synthesized in our lab¹⁵. 3-chloropropyltris(trimethylsiloxy) silane were purchased from Adamas Reagent Co., Ltd.. Methanol, concentrated hydrochloric acid, anhydrous sodium sulfate, dimethyl formamide and ethyl acetate were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. Sodium azide was purchased from Dongyang Tianyu Chemical Co., Ltd.

Analyses and characterizations

Infrared spectroscopic measurements were performed in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 1.0 cm^{-1} on a Nicolet Avatar 5700 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectrophotometer. The sample was put into the hot cell of Thermo's HT-32 which was

programmable to a heating rate of 3°C/min under air atmosphere. The static contact angle measurements with the probe liquids (ultrapure water and diiodomethane) were carried out on a Powereach contact angle measurement instrument (JC 2000D3) at room temperature. Differential scanning calorimetric (DSC) analyses were carried out with a TA Q2000 instrument (TA Instruments, USA) at a scanning rate of 10°C/min under nitrogen flow (50 mL/min). The surface morphologies of the composites were analyzed by S-4800 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) instrument (Hitachi, Japan). Flexural measurements were carried out with a Universal Testing Machine DDL100 (Cimach, China) according to China Standard GB/T 2570-1997 at a crosshead rate of 2 mm/min. Specimens with dimensions of 45 mm×15 mm×2 mm and 20 mm×6 mm×2 mm were tested in a three-point loading mode. The data presented were an average of measurements for five samples.

Synthesis of octa(azidopropyl) polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (OAPS)

Octa(chloropropyl) POSS (OCPS) was synthesized by the following method. 1800 mL methanol, 79.5 g (0.4 mol) 3-chloropropyltrimethoxysilane, and 90 mL concentrated hydrochloric acid were mixed. The hydrolysis and rearrangement reactions were allowed to carry out for 7 weeks and 19.3 g colorless crystals OCPS were obtained after dried in vacuo at 80 °C for 7 h.

OAPS was synthesized by following the method described by Li et al.¹⁹ (Scheme 1). OCPS [(C₃H₆Cl)₈Si₈O₁₂] 1.0 g (1.0 mmol) and 15 mL of DMF were added into a round bottom flask. Sodium azide 0.78 g (12.0 mmol) was added to the solution. The reaction was kept at 70 °C for 60 h. Then deionized water was added into the reaction mixture, and ethyl acetate was added to extract the product. The ethyl acetate solution was separated through a separating funnel and subjected to rotary evaporation to obtain colorless viscous liquid. The product was dried in a vacuum oven for 12 h at 80 °C. ¹H-NMR(CDCl₃, 400MHz): δ 3.3 (-CH₂), 1.7 (-CH₂), 0.7 (-CH₂).

Scheme 1: Preparation of octa(chloropropyl) POSS and octa(azidopropyl) POSS

Preparation of OAPS-PSA resins

Novel OAPS-PSA resins were prepared from a PSA resin and OAPS in various weight ratios. OAPS and PSA were weighed and dissolved in THF, stirred to obtain a homogeneous solution at room temperature. The solvent THF was removed by a rotary evaporator at 40°C, and then the resins were dried in vacuum to afford light yellow resins. In the preparation of a series of OAPS-PSA resins, the weight ratios of OAPS to PSA were 1:99, 3:97 and 5:95, and thus the relative resins obtained were named as 1%OAPS-PSA, 3%OAPS-PSA and 5%OAPS-PSA, respectively. FT-IR(KBr) analysis: 1088cm⁻¹(Si-O-Si), 2108cm⁻¹ (-N₃), 2153cm⁻¹ (-C≡C-), 2963cm⁻¹ (-CH₃), 3291cm⁻¹ (≡C-H);

The curing process was shown as follows: the resins were heated to and kept at 150°C for 2 h, 170 °C for 2 h, 210 °C for 2 h, and 250 °C for 4 h based on DSC curves to gain OAPS-PSA thermosets. Scheme 2 outlines the reactions between OAPS and PSA.

Scheme 2: Preparation of OAPS-PSA resin

Preparation of CF/OAPS-PSA composites

The composites were prepared from 2D T300 carbon fiber plain fabrics and OAPS-PSA resins or the PSA resin, respectively. Curing was performed in a compression-molding machine by compression molding, and the content of the resin in composites was controlled at about 33 wt%. The curing process was shown as follows: 170 °C for 2 h, 210 °C for 2 h, and 250 °C for 4 h, with the molding

pressure of 3MPa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Curing behavior of OAPS-PSA resins

Figure 1 shows the DSC curves for PSA and OAPS-PSA resins, and the details are listed in Table 1. In the DSC curve of PSA, an exothermic peak within the temperature range from 195 to 270°C is displayed, which is assignable to the curing reactions of C≡C (including ethynyls and ethynylenes) to form crosslinked networks. It is noted that with the incorporation of OAPS, the DSC curves are analogous to that of PSA, but the exothermic peaks appear in a lower temperature region of OAPS-PSA, with exothermal heat reduction of 50-68 J/g. It is due to the difference between two kinds of reactions, i.e., the azide/alkyne 1, 3-dipolar cycloaddition and polymerization of alkynes. As shown in Tab. 1, the exothermal heat of OAPS-PSA resins reduces, implying that the crosslinking reaction of ethynyls has a higher enthalpy than that of the triazole ring formation.

Figure 1: DSC curves of PSA, 1%OAPS-PSA, 3%OAPS-PSA, and 5%OAPS-PSA

Sample	T _i (°C)	T _p (°C)	Exothermal heat (J/g)
PSA	212.1	238.4	472.9
1%OAPS-PSA	205.1	236.9	422.3
3%OAPS-PSA	195.2	228.1	420.2
5%OAPS-PSA	207.8	223.9	404.6

Table 1: DSC analysis results of PSA and OAPS-PSA resins

FT-IR spectra of 5% OAPS-PSA resin at various temperatures are shown in Figure 2. The -CH₃ stretching vibrations at 2963 cm⁻¹ are used as the internal reference. The intensity of characteristic signals for the -N₃ groups at 2108 cm⁻¹ and the ≡CH groups at 3291 cm⁻¹ are found to decrease with

the temperature increasing, which shows the progressive reactions between OAPS and PSA. In the spectrum of 5%OAPS-PSA resin at 213°C, the peak at 2108 cm⁻¹ disappears, which demonstrates the completely reaction of the azide group with ethynyls or ethynylenes to form triazole rings.

The variation of the functional groups during heating can be investigated. According to Beer-Lambert law²⁰, the conversion ratio (α) of the functional groups is obtained by calculating the intensity of the signals at 2108 cm⁻¹ and 3291 cm⁻¹, on the following equation:

$$\alpha = \frac{C_0 - C}{C_0} = \frac{I_0 - I}{I_0} \quad (1)$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of a group, and C the concentration of the group at temperature T . I_0 is initial intensity of the group and I intensity of the group at temperature T . The concentration is proportional to the intensity of absorption of the group.

Figure 3 shows the conversion ratio of terminal ethynyls and azide groups with the temperature increasing. The conversion ratio of azide groups (α_a) increases immediately with the increasing temperature, and reaches nearly 100% when heated to 213°C, illustrating that the azide groups can react completely with alkynyls. At 171°C, the α_a and the conversion ratio of terminal ethynyls (α_e) reach to 77% and 14% respectively, indicating that the reaction between terminal ethynyls and azide groups happens mainly below this temperature. The α_e increases tardily before 171°C, implies that the cross-linking reaction of ethynyls happens at a bit higher temperature. It should be noted that both of the reactions could be easily initiated under heating.

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra for 5% OAPS-PSA resin heated at increasing temperature

Figure 3: The conversion ratio of azides and ethynyls in 5%OAPS-PSA resin versus elevating temperature

The properties of OAPS-PSA thermosets

SEM morphologies of the fractured surfaces of the samples (Figure 4) are used to illustrate the dispersion of OAPS and compatibility of OAPS in PSA resin. Figure 4(a) presents the smooth surface of the PSA thermoset. Figure 4(b) exhibits a featureless morphology with some spherical agglomerates formed with maximum diameters of 3.5 μm , which are likely to be POSS-rich domains¹³. To observe the morphology in detail, the partial area in Figure 4(b) is magnified as shown in Figure 4(c).

Figure 4: SEM morphologies of fractured surface of (a) cured PSA; (b-c) 5% OAPS-PSA

The surface properties of the thermosets are investigated by static contact angle of water (Figure 5) which decreases from 112.0° for the PSA thermoset to 80.0° for 5%OAPS-PSA thermoset. It suggests that most POSS modified polymers become more hydrophobic due to the cage-like nanostructure of POSS²¹. While the OAPS-PSA thermosets exhibit smaller water contact angles than the PSA thermoset, indicating that the POSS with triazole rings play an important role. The surface free energies of the resins containing various percentages of OAPS are further investigated and calculated according to the geometric mean model^{22, 23}:

$$\cos\theta = \frac{2}{\gamma_L} \left[(\gamma_L^d \gamma_S^d)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (\gamma_L^p \gamma_S^p)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] - 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma_S = \gamma_S^d + \gamma_S^p \quad (3)$$

Where θ is the contact angle, γ_L the liquid surface tension, γ_S the surface free energy; γ_S^d and γ_S^p are the dispersive and polar components of γ_S , respectively. The treated results are listed in Table 2. From Table 2, it is seen that with the increase of the OAPS content, the total surface free energies of the composites increase from 21.09 mN/m to 36.80 mN/m. It is noted the polar component is very sensitive to the concentration of OAPS, suggesting that the POSS with triazole rings can significantly enhance the polarity and the surface energy of the thermosets.

Figure 5: Water contact angle measurements for (a) PSA thermosets; (b) 1% OAPS-PSA thermosets; (c) 3% OAPS-PSA thermosets; (d) 5% OAPS-PSA thermosets

Sample	Contact angle (°)		Surface energy (J/m ²)		
	Water	Diiodomethane	γ_S^d	γ_S^p	γ_S
PSA	112.0±0.1	66.7±0.2	21.06	0.03	21.09
1%OAPS-PSA	106.9±0.3	63.8±0.4	22.86	0.49	23.35
3%OAPS-PSA	96.2±1.9	61.8±1.1	25.44	2.20	27.64
5%OAPS-PSA	80.0±0.4	47.4±1.9	31.50	5.30	36.80

Table 2: Static contact angle and surface energy of PSA and OAPS-PSA thermosets

Mechanical properties of T300/OAPS-PSA

To investigate mechanical reinforcement effect of OAPS-PSA resins, the T300/OAPS-PSA and T300/PSA composites were prepared from 2D T300 carbon fiber plain fabrics, OAPS-PSA resin or PSA resin, respectively.

The results of mechanical properties containing flexural strength and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) are presented in Figure 6. It is obvious that the T300/OAPS-PSA composites exhibit notably high flexural strength and ILSS over the T300/PSA composite. As the T300/OAPS-PSA, the flexural strength is increased from 237 MPa for T300/PSA to a maximum of 293 MPa for T300/3%OAPS-PSA composite, with almost 24% increment. The presence of POSS with triazole rings enhances the polarity of OAPS-PSA thermosets, and the POSS aggregations is helpful to distribute the load and transfer it from resins to T300²⁴, in which the aggregates can probably work as reinforcement for the composites. The ILSS of T300/PSA composites is 16 MPa, which indicates there is a weak bonding between fibers and PSA resin. The carbonaceous nature of fiber surface and the

non-polar aromatic structure of PSA result in weak interaction between fibers and PSA thermosets. The ILSS of 5%T300/OAPS-PSA composite is increased by 19% to 19.3 MPa with the incorporation of 5 wt% OAPS. The results indicate that the POSS units with triazole rings play an important role in improving the mechanical properties of the composites.

Figure 6: Mechanical properties of T300/PSA and T300/OAPS-PSA composites (a) flexural strength; (b) interlaminar shear strength

SEM morphologies of T300/PSA and T300/OAPS-PSA composites are presented in Figure 7. Figure 7 (a) shows the fracture of T300/PSA composite. Long carbon fibers in the composites are exposed, and the surface of carbon fibers is smooth, almost no resin fragments adhered on, which indicates the adhesion between fibers and resin is weak. After the introduction of OAPS (Figure 7 (b)), the fibers are embedded in resins and the interfacial adhesion is obviously improved. The POSS units with triazole rings increase the polarity and surface energy of the OAPS-PSA thermosets, and improve the interfacial adhesion between fibers and the matrix, which corresponds with the test results of the mechanical property.

Figure 7: SEM morphologies of the composites: (a) T300/PSA; (b) T300/1%OAPS-PSA; (c) T300/3%OAPS-PSA; (d) T300/5%OAPS-PSA

CONCLUSIONS

Octa(azidopropyl) POSS (OAPS) can be introduced into PSA resins by “click” polymerization of N_3 and $-C\equiv C-$ groups and then the obtained OAPS-PSA resins were characterized by FT-IR. The POSS units with triazole rings form spherical aggregates with the maximum diameters of 3.5 μm in the OAPS-PSA thermosets. The static contact angle shows the incorporation of OAPS makes the

polarity and surface energy of the thermosets increase dramatically. The flexural test results indicate the flexural strength of a T300/5%OAPS-PSA composite arrives at 293 MPa and increases by 24% as compared with that of the T300/PSA composite. It is supposed that the POSS units with triazole rings enhance the polarity of OAPS-PSA thermosets, and the resulting POSS aggregations are helpful to improve of the mechanical properties of the composite.

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